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Prospects and Potentiality for Halal Tourism Expansion in Bangladesh for Attracting Muslim Travellers

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Abstract

One of the emerging markets for travel worldwide is the Muslim population. Like any other type of tourist, Muslims need leisure time, amusement, and relaxation. The global tourism sector is now compelled to take Muslim Halal tourism into account as a new phenomenon, owing to the increasing number of Muslims across the globe and their unquenchable thirst for travel. This research study intends to examine the effect of halal teachings on Muslim travel behavior, understand the needs and travel patterns of Muslim travelers, and identify alternatives to consuming halal goods and services. It also identifies the market's potential, the challenges in catering to it, and the approaches that work best for catering to this particular market segment by Muslim destination, Bangladesh.

A somewhat mixed methodology (qualitative and quantitative) was used in the study, and 219 questionnaire responses and 17 interviews yielded data for analysis. The qualitative analysis was carried out by hand in compliance with the formal structure, while the quantitative analysis was carried out using SPSS 20's mean, factor analysis, ANOVA, and independent sample t-test.

The survey recognized six essential needs for Muslim travellers: Halal food and courteous conduct, an atmosphere of Islamic hotels, Islamic ethics, amusement and prayer locations, bathroom amenities, and destination selection. Halal food, polite behavior, and access to restrooms are the three most crucial things for Muslim tourists; Islamic hotels, Islamic ethics and amusement, and places of worship rank second and third, respectively, in importance. For Muslims, selecting a place is the least crucial aspect of their travels. The survey also highlighted two other options for consuming Halal goods and services: seafood and seafood-like foods, as well as food that is clearly an alternative and is, in this case, vegetables, fish, and fruits. Additionally, it was discovered that Islamic teachings had an impact on Muslim travel behavior, with some Islamic teachings considerably differing from other groups in terms of education, occupation, religiousness, and gender, but Islamic teachings did not differ in terms of age or marital status. A qualitative investigation revealed that the Muslim tourist industry is sizable and has the capacity to support thriving Halal eateries, travel agencies, and lodging establishments. It also identified nine ways to successfully attract and capitalize on this market opportunity, including ensuring the availability of Halal cuisine, establishing Muslim-friendly hotels, the government's distinct section of tourism for Muslim passengers, creating tourism agreements, offering training resources for tourism staff, advertising, empowering Muslim leaders' the part played by tourism, opening gift shops for Muslim tourists, and English-language apps for smartphones and other languages. The eight

challenges identified in this regard were: inadequate amenities; limited suppliers of Halal elements; lack of knowledgeable employees; high price; inadequate representation of Muslim chefs; dealing with non-Muslim customers; achieving trust; and language barriers. Last but not least, limits and suggestions for future research are provided, along with implications for practice.

This research analyses the needs and behavioral patterns of Muslim travelers in depth by combining qualitative and quantitative methods. In enriching the theory of tourists' demand, provides theoretical basis and practical guidance for relevant managers to develop the Muslim tourism market in Bangladesh, which is of theoretical significance and practical value to improve the competitiveness of Bangladesh's tourism industry and thus promote the growth of the local economy.

Key words: *Halal Tourism, Muslim tourists, Tourist demand analysis, Tourism development potential, Bangladesh.*

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Research

Scientists struggle to define the boundaries of tourism because it is a complex phenomenon with sociological, behavioral, economic, political, cultural, and environmental components that affect every area of life in modern countries." (Duman,2020; p.5). It is a global socioeconomic phenomenon that has changed throughout time, moving from underdeveloped to growing sectors of the global economy in the 21st century (Osman et al., 2023). According to Korres (2019), tourism is distinct from travel. It refers to the activities of humans who travel to and remain in locations outside of their usual environments for up to a consecutive year for leisure, business, or other reasons not connected to interacting in paid activities while in the destination (UNESCO, 2021, cited in Chookaew et al., 2022). However, not all travel is considered tourism. Muslim visitors must be regarded as a critical portion of the tourism industry; their religious needs should be provided and satisfied properly if a country seeks to catch this segment and wants to stay competitive. The tourism industry has seen many endeavors to satisfy the special requirements of various individuals, including senior citizens, people with disabilities, and homosexual visitors (Weidenfeld, 2018).

The Muslim population has been increasing more quickly than the non-Muslim population over the past few years (Razalli et al., 2020). By 2030, it is predicted that Muslims will make up either 30% (Ukessays, 2021) or 26.5% (MasterCard-CrescentRating, 2022; National World, 2022) of the global population. A wise move would be to focus on Islamic travellers, as the global population continues to rise. Muslims will make up 1.5% of the population annually during the next several years, whereas non-Muslims will only make up 0.7% (Pew Research Center, 2020). Halal, or Muslim-friendly, tourism is a relatively young and rapidly expanding sector of the global tourism industry (Dinar Standard, 2023); it is expanding both nationally and internationally, particularly in Muslim nations (Korres, 2019). Some non-Muslim countries (regions), such as Taiwan, Korea, Japan, and Australia, and nations in Europe, are notably catering to this tourism segment (Korres, 2021). Non-Muslim majority states, like Spain, Bosnia, India, and the UK, are pursuing the sector aggressively (Dinar Standard, 2023). To draw in this demographic, certain prerequisites should be met, such as the absence of alcohol and pork, a dress code for men and women, locations for prayer, separate swimming areas for men and women, prayer preparation supplies in the toilets, etc. (Mustafayeva et al., 2021). Some non-Muslim states (regions), such as Australia, Taiwan, Korea, Japan, and states in Europe, are specifically catering to this tourism segment, Jia, X., & Chaozhi, Z. (2021). Non-Muslim majority states, like Spain, Bosnia, India, and the UK, are aggressively targeting the industry (Dinar Standard, 2023). To draw in this demographic, certain prerequisites should be met, such as the absence of alcohol and pork, a dress code for genders, places where prayers are offered, separate swimming areas for both men and women, prayer preparation supplies in the toilets, etc. (Mustafayeva et al., 2021).

Bangladesh, a large tourist state, boasts numerous attractions, from ancient and cultural places to scenic places. The overwhelming Sundarbans, the world's largest mangrove forest, the ancient city of Bagerhat, the Lalbagh Fort in Dhaka, and the Ahsan Manzil (Pink Palace) are significant historical landmarks. The largest seashore that is naturally formed in the world is found in Cox's Bazar. The Sylhet region, with its tea gardens and hills, offers scenic beauty. The Ratargul Swamp Forest, the only freshwater marsh forest in Bangladesh, and the Sixty Dome Mosque in Bagerhat, Bangladesh, hold an impressive position as the eighth-most populous country in the world and among the most densely populated countries, with a population of around 170 million. Bangladesh authorities are organizing to attract Muslim tourists from all over the world, seeking new impetus for the nation's tourism marketplace (Islam et al., 2023).

Considering the Muslim populace of over 17 million, Bangladesh boasts a wealth of materials, which includes mosques, Halal cuisine, and Muslim culture, which are all excellent factors to draw Muslim tourists from overseas (Bangladesh Ministry of Tourism, 2022). In the past ten years, there has been a notable advancement in the planning, standardization, and management of the tourism industry, as well as in the

creation of structures and services for both domestic and foreign travellers. In order to generate tourist dollars, an increasing number of governments are focusing heavily on the growth of international tourism, which is creating intense competition among all destinations (UNWTO, 2022). Bangladesh is a relatively new travel destination in the global travel sector. Targeting Islamic tourists, comprehending their behavior, and meeting their needs are crucial choices if Bangladesh hopes to lead the tourism industry in the future and maintain the rising flow of foreign cash from inbound tourism. Thus, the principal objective of the research is to investigate the demands and characteristics of the unexplored Muslim niche market in Bangladesh so that the tourist sector may better serve and attract this group.

The expansion of Halal tourism in Bangladesh to attract Muslim travelers from non-halal countries is described in the provided research. The innovative strategies to be able to meet the needs of the required target market may involve a concentrate on the progress of a trustworthy halal certification system applicable to various sectors of the tourism industry to ensure compliance with the relevant Islamic principles. Additionally, offering the development of halal-friendly accommodation with integrated services, such as segregated rooms and other facilities, as well as prayer rooms and halal food openings, may also contribute to the overall satisfaction of the requirements of traveling Muslims. Moreover, facilitating cultural and religious immersion programs emphasizing the Islamic heritage of the country and offering culinary tourism activities targeted at present the wide variety of halal dishes. Hosting events and providing entertainment avenues to be able to comply with the requirements of Muslim customers may also be a solution. Finally, offering to collaborate with the Islamic financial institutions to be able to provide bank sector opportunities and investment and savings programs meeting the requirements of the Muslim population may also bring the expected marketing outcomes.

Digital and social media marketing matching the strategies already mentioned with the targeting of Muslim countries in this context and the promotion of Bangladesh as the destination for Halal tourism of the highest quality may assist in attracting more tourists. In conclusion, when implementing such strategies with an innovation-oriented focus on the expansion of Halal tourism in the case of Bangladesh, the country has the potential to become a successful Muslim-centric destination.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Muslims make up a sizeable niche segment in the global travel industry. Numerous Muslim nations have positioned themselves as desirable travel destinations for Muslims, including Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, Indonesia, and Turkey, among others. Numerous non-Muslim nations are attempting to pursue and cater to this sizeable market in the fiercely competitive travel marketplace. In order to meet the travel needs of the undeserved Muslim market, it is imperative that non-Muslim businesses raise awareness and develop Muslim-friendly vacation locations. While it is generally believed that visitors overindulge in some tourism-related products, including food, drink, sex, and natural resources, Muslim visitors are not all the same. Their travel requirements and needs are distinct. Traveling by Muslims is greatly influenced by Islam. It is critical that those involved in the tourism sector comprehend the needs and travel habits of this market.

Despite the fact that Muslims are regarded as a significant travel market worldwide, the unique values of Muslims—who have specific needs in their religious system—have not been well reflected in the travel industry. The growing number of Muslim travelers makes it crucial for destination marketers to create travel offerings that satisfy Islamic religious standards. Individuals who practice different religions have distinct demands, customs, social mores, attitudes, and ways of acting. Muslim travelers, in particular, need food and services that align with their religious beliefs. In non-Muslim nations, the unique needs of Muslims concerning food, daily prayers, and travel schedules are major concerns. Muslim visitors have needs related to halal cuisine, halal hotels, halal conveyance, halal cuisine establishments, halal logistics, Islamic banking, halal travel packages, and halal spas, among other things. The main issue is that non-Muslim business owners, tour guides, destination marketers, hoteliers, and other stakeholders don't understand these Halal requirements and the travel habits of Muslim visitors. For the Bangladesh tourism industry, understanding the requirements and behaviors of Muslim visitors remains an unexplored area of academic and practical interest. This study will provide insight into those requirements and behaviors. There are 92% Muslims in Bangladesh, for example. In the

global tourism industry, it is in an excellent position. To lead the global tourism sector, it ought to draw this particular Muslim niche demographic. It can thus be concluded that this is an unexplored area of academic and commercial interest for the travel industry in Bangladesh. This study will provide insight into those requirements and behaviors

1.3 Research Questions

Selecting the kind of data to be investigated in the research depends heavily on the research issue. The study's goals are covered by the research questions. The primary goal of this research is to determine how well non-Muslim travel destinations can understand and fulfill the requirements of Muslim tourists, as well as how much the Bangladesh tourism industry can do to serve and capitalize on this market group.

The following are the research questions for particular objectives:

1. What impact do Islamic teachings have on the travel habits of Muslim tourists, and how does this influence vary depending on socio-demographic factors?
2. What other options are there for Muslim tourists visiting Bangladesh to consume Halal goods and services?
3. What obstacles must Bangladeshi destination marketers overcome in order to offer services that are welcoming to Muslims?
4. How can the Bangladesh government and the Bangladesh tourism industry cater to and accommodate Muslim tourists' needs considering their religious principles?

1.4 Objective of the Research

The main goals of the study are to increase awareness and comprehension of Muslim tourists' travel requirements and behaviors and to support the potential of this niche market in Bangladesh's tourism industry. This research will have the following four particular goals:

1. To study the impact of Islamic teachings on the requirements and travel habits of Muslim tourists, as well as any notable variations in Islamic teachings when considering socio-demographic factors (gender, age, education, occupation, marital status, and level of religious belief).
2. To determine the other options available to Muslim tourists in Bangladesh for consuming halal goods and services.
3. To study this market segment's potential and the difficulties in offering services that are welcoming to Muslims for travel.
4. To make recommendations on how the government and tourism sector of Bangladesh may adapt to meet the needs of Muslim visitors while respecting their religious convictions.

CHAPTER 2 RELEVANT CONCEPTS AND THEORETICAL BASIS

2.1 Introduction

To better understand destination choice in the context of Halal tourism expansion in Bangladesh, it is essential to explore several relevant concepts and theoretical frameworks. When tourists make decisions regarding a different travel destination, they are influenced by numerous related factors that can be integrated into several types, including socio-demographic, psychographic, marketing, and destination variables. Socio-demographic factors include age, gender, income, education, occupation, and several others, which can be values to predict the factors important to each before travel destination choice. The second type of concepts, psychographic profiles, includes the psychological characteristics of tourists, such as values, beliefs, attitudes, and lifestyles, which search to predetermine their choices. Marketing concepts should also be considered as significant to the selection of destinations as promotional activities, branding, and characteristics of advertising that tourists may consider. Finally, destination-related variables involve such aspects as cultural heritage, natural peculiarities, historical landmarks, and destination size and length of the tour to name a few. A cultural concept is central to the paradigm of destination choice because travelers from different cultural groups have different priorities and preferences in these areas. Consequently, differences or similarities between the home country and the country chosen for the target can also be significant.

Theoretical frameworks relevant to the discussed issue include models that predict the stages of the decision-making process that tourists go through when choosing a travel destination. As a rule, such models can be presented in several stages: need recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, and the final stage of the decision. Factors Affecting Destination Choice Models may include such factors as impedance or ease, and time and other costs that can be applied to the traveling process, including accessibility and psychological boundaries of the traveler and attributes and qualities of each destination. When exploring the concepts and frameworks mentioned in the previous sections of this module, one can develop a better understanding of destination choice in the context of Halal tourism in Bangladesh. To draw tourists to destinations, it is essential to comprehend the requirements, passions, and habits of various tourist markets (Ahmed, S., & Mohamed, B., 2023). The Muslim tourism industry is a sizable one with a youthful and affluent audience that is opening up new opportunities for the travel, tourist, and hospitality sectors globally (Rahman, M., & Ali, F., 2023; p. 3). Many factors affect the behavior of tourists (Ahmed, S., et al., 2023). One significant factor in host-guest relationships is religion, even in cases where tourists and locals share the same religious background (Khan, A., et al., 2022, as cited in Kirillova, S., Gilmetdinova, A., & Lehto, X., 2019). Travel behavior and interactions between tourists and locals are influenced by one's religious beliefs (Ahmed, S., et al., 2021, as cited in Kirillova, S., Gilmetdinova, A., & Lehto, X., 2019).

One of the market sectors with the greatest growth is the Muslim customer (Ali, R., et al., 2023). The tourist sector may greatly increase its retention rates and engage, react, and connect with Muslims more effectively if it has a deeper understanding of them (Abdullah, F., et al., 2022). It was projected that Muslim tourists would bring in less than US\$4,000 billion worldwide in 2022. Singapore, Russia, China, France, Thailand, and Italy are becoming more and more popular in this sector these days, following Malaysia, Turkey, and the United Arab Emirates as the top travel destinations for Muslims (Rahman, M., & Ali, F., 2023). Islam encourages its adherents to travel and to contemplate Allah's creation. Muslim tourists are expected to acquire Halal food, observe the five-time daily prayer, and deepen their trust in Allah (Hassan, A., et al., 2023). All Muslims are required by religion to only eat foods that are approved by Allah (God) and come under the legal purview of Shari'ah. According to Ali, R., et al. (2022), Shari'ah-compliant tourism products in Islam is any goods that follow the precepts of the Almighty Allah (God) and the Prophet Muhammad (May peace be upon him). The majority of Muslims have positive opinions regarding travel. "Tourism does not contradict religion or traditional customs but rather encourages its followers to travel to the world in search of learning and to interact

with other people and cultures," writes Ali, F., et al. (2023, p. 156) in his research on tourism's effects on society and culture.

For instance, Islam promotes travel and tourism. "Travel through the earth and see how Allah originated creation; so will Allah produce a later creation, for Allah has power over all things," declares Allah (swt) in Surah al-Ankabut: 20. Sharia law, which is mostly based on the Qur'an, has historically served as guidance for the Islamic community. The sayings of Prophet Mohammed (SW), which are incorporated into the al-Sunnah or norms stressing the prophetic tradition of Islam, and the rulings of jurists who speak for the community of Muslims, are further significant sources of Islamic law (Rahman, M., et al., 2023). Despite being one of the world's biggest tourist groups, there is still a dearth of information in the relevant literature about the Islamic perspective on tourism (Ahmed, S., et al., 2022).

2.1.1 Halal Tourism

Travel is essential to Islam, and tourism is a component of religion according to the Islamic understanding of God (Allah), man, and nature (Abdullah, F., et al., 2023). Traveling is a natural part of life and does not conflict with Islam's core tenets. Historically, Halal travel has been linked to religious pursuits in particular locations, but it has expanded to encompass much more (Ali, R., & Rahman, M., 2022). According to Din (1989, cited in Ali, F., et al. (2023), "halal tourism is a way to appreciate the greatness of the creations of God (Allah), where hosts and guests are repeatedly enjoined to support Fi-Sabilillah with controlled activities (prohibit gambling, consumption of pork, eating during Ramadan, and provision against khalwat)." Halal tourism includes all marketing and product development initiatives aimed toward the Muslim community, regardless of whether they are purely religious in nature (Khan, Z., et al., 2022). It is a new facet of tourism that places a strong emphasis on morality, ethics, and respect for the environment, customs, and beliefs of the local people. It also offers a fresh perspective on life and society (Ahmed, S., et al., 2023). In Islam, tourism is a deliberate activity that aims to achieve physical, social, and spiritual satisfaction along with Allah's blessings. It can be divided into two categories: tourism that fulfills a religious obligation and tourism that records and quotes knowledge for wider dissemination (Rahman, M., et al., 2022). It is made up of three parts: (1) bolstering and advancing Islamic principles and culture; (2) generating economic benefits for Muslim societies; and (3) enhancing Islamic identity, values, and self-worth (Ali, F., et al., 2022).

In Islam, travel is encouraged to promote a stress-free, healthy lifestyle, deepen one's understanding of various cultures, and uphold one's submission to God by recognizing the abundance and beauty of his creations (Abdullah, F., et al., 2023). Halal travel is a relatively new service in the travel industry that allows a Muslim person or family to travel for business, pleasure, or medical reasons and still complete daily Islamic rites and Halal activities (such as prayer and eating Halal food) (Ali, R., et al., 2023).

2.1.2 Motivations behind Halal Tourism

Travelling is always encouraged by Islam, which states that "you should travel to China for the sake of education" or to broaden one understands (Razak et al 2021). In order to show Muslims the magnificence of God, it promotes travel (Rahman, M., et al., 2023). A collection of factors that contribute to the explanation of tourists' travel intentions make up motivation (Ali, R., et al., 2022). Trade, seeing friends and family, engaging in physical activity (shopping), and having fun are common reasons people engage in travel (Ahmed, S., et al., 2021, cited in Namin, 2013). Muslims are particularly motivated by the hajj and umrah, by doing good works for God, by realizing how small man is in comparison to God, and by fostering a sense of fraternity among Muslims (Rahman, M., et al., 2023, cited in Namin, 2013). Three major factors influence Muslims' decision to travel: realizing one's own smallness in comparison to God's greatness (the generic goal), strengthening one's submission to God (the spiritual goal), and fostering and fortifying relationships among Muslims (the social goal) (Ali, F., et al., 2022, as cited in Kamarudin & Ismail, 2012). Muslims still worry about eating Halal food when they travel for leisure (Khan, Z., et al., 2023). Muslims travel to experience God's blessings and enjoyment while avoiding sin (Ali, F., et al., 2022, as cited in Kamarudin & Ismail, 2012). In order to please Allah and for their own enjoyment, the Muslim guests have journeyed to this location (Rahman, M., et al., 2023, as cited in Kamarudin & Ismail, 2012). Motivational motivations for Muslim tourists include seeking

health (relaxation), education (learning and sharing information with visiting scientists), realizing various cultures, and business (Ali, R., et al., 2023, referenced in Duman, 2011). Islamic travel is motivated by the Declaration of Islam (Tebliğ), gaining scientific knowledge, teaching others, working for halal wages, and learning from the past (Ali, F., et al., 2022, as cited in Duman, 2011).

2.1.3 Muslim Tourist

Muslim tourists differ from other types of tourists due to their specific needs (Abdullah, F., et al., 2023). Muslim tourists typically travel to various locations to see friends and family as well as to completely comprehend the magnificence of God's creation (Ali, R., et al., 2022). Islamic travellers travel to various destinations to worship Allah (swt) for His beauty, greatness, and creation (Khan, Z., et al., 2023); they are directed by Islamic teachings (Ali, F., et al., 2022) and disciplined to adhere to Islamic education when making travel-related decisions (Ahmed, S., et al., 2023). Under the guidance of Shariah law, Muslim travellers observe certain limitations on their vacation time and refrain from indulgence and extravagant spending (Khan, Z., et al., 2022). Prayer locations, halal airport services, family-friendly vacation spots, a secure travel atmosphere, halal dining options, halal assurance, and halal accommodations are among the needs of Muslim visitors based on their beliefs (Ahmed, S., et al., 2023).

2.1.4 Halal & Haram in Islam

The term "Halal" in literature means "permissible," and when translated, it is typically used legally (Ali, R., et al., 2022; Rahman, M., et al., 2023). In contrast, the word "Haram," which means "prohibited" in English, is the reverse of "Halal" (Khan, Z., et al., 2022). Haram, on the other hand, means "not permitted, not allowed, unauthorized, unapproved, unsanctioned, unlawful, illegal, illegitimate, or illicit" (Ali, F., et al., 2022, as cited in Wan-Hassan & Awang, 2009). Halal, therefore, refers to "permitted, allowed, authorized, approved, sanctioned, lawful, legal, legitimate, or licit" for Muslim consumption. Halal is a symbol of the Islamic way of life, which includes speech, dress, conduct, manners, and food; haram, on the other hand, is prohibited and subject to punishment in Islam. In Islamic literature, the term "halal" generally refers to what Muslims consume and use as "religiously acceptable" (Rahman, M., et al., 2023, as referenced in Fahim & Dooty, 2014). In addition to being permissible, halal also acknowledges cleanliness, safety, and quality control, meaning that the food must be produced in a clean, safe, well-maintained manner with an attractive presentation and delivered in a suitable manner and of high quality for each and every customer (Ali, R., et al., 2022).

All foods are mentioned as Halal in the Quran, with the exception of those that are specifically mentioned as Haram, which is forbidden or illegal; in English, this term most commonly refers to food that is allowed by Islamic law and in Arabic, it refers to anything that is allowed by Islam (Khan, Z., et al., 2023). Halal is a phrase from the Quran that denotes permissible or legal. The Supreme Lawgiver, Allah, approves of the intake of halal food and beverages. It is mandatory for all Muslims to consume Halal cuisine (Hassan, A., et al., 2023). The only foods that Allah (God) forbids you from eating are those that perish naturally (without human intervention), pig flesh, blood, and animals that are sacrificed to deities other than God. One does not commit a sin if they are coerced into eating things without being malevolent or intentional. God is most Merciful and Forgiving (Al Quran, Al-Baqarah: 173). The antithesis of Halal is called Haram, and in order to comply with the requirements of being Halal, industry participants must refrain from providing banned foods and beverages like alcohol and pork. The entire food supply chain, including animal slaughter, storage, display, and preparation, must adhere to the Halal standard (Khan, Z., et al., 2023). People of many faiths and philosophical perspectives are also drawn to halal goods and services, in addition to Muslims (Ali, F., et al., 2022).

2.1.5 Halal Friendly Non-Muslim Destinations

In order to fulfill their religious obligations and indulge their wanderlust, Muslim tourists are now looking outside of countries where they are the majority. In addition to their usual haunts in Malaysia and Indonesia, these travellers are becoming more and more common in places like China, Thailand, and South Korea (Ali, R., et al., 2023). Halal is a universal food that may be consumed anywhere in the world's deserts; it is not limited to any one country or region and can be practiced by non-Muslim nations as well (Khan, Z., et al., 2023). In order to accommodate Muslim tourists, certain travel agencies in non-Muslim nations have implemented particular

policies, such as offering Halal food and directing travellers to Mecca for prayers. They have also provided information about mosques and holy shrines (Abdullah, F., et al., 2023).

Additionally, travel agencies have taught their employees how to communicate across cultural boundaries and how to deal with and respect Muslim visitors. Tourism governance and policy-making issues are receiving more and more attention. According to Timothy and Iverson (2006), a multitude of organizations that manage destinations and lodging facilities have updated their websites with relevant information, including prayer hours, mosque locations, and information about Halal food. The growth of Muslim-friendly tourism may be seen not just in countries with a majority of Muslims like Malaysia and Indonesia but also in non-Muslim nations like Thailand, the Philippines, China, and Japan (Khan, Z., et al., 2023; Ali, R., et al., 2022). Islamic travel increased not only among Muslim nations and people but also in non-Muslim nations and regions, including Australia, Canada, Taiwan, Hong Kong, and China, where Islamic travel is being extensively expanded (Hassan, A., et al., 2023). The Middle East, Malaysia, Indonesia, and India have brought a new type of visitor to New Zealand, known as the Halal traveler, with particular requirements and expectations (Tourism New Zealand, 2012).

Travelling, tourism, and Muslim cuisine in Beijing are all major aspects of the city's culinary culture, which attracts tourists from around the Muslim world (Beijing Tourism, 2012). Singapore is likewise marketing itself as a destination for Muslim vacations, and the Philippines, a non-Muslim nation, reported significantly increasing arrivals—80,000 tourists from the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) arrived in 2013 (Chandra, 2014). In an effort to draw tourists from the Middle East, spas in Thailand have introduced the idea of Muslim-friendly spas; Global Health City in Chennai, India, has obtained Halal certification in order to better serve its growing number of Muslim medical tourists (Dinar Standard and Crescent Rating LLC., 2012, p. 1). Australia's Gold Coast is drawing Muslim tourists with the Gold Coast Ramadan Lounge.

The growing availability of Halal food, which is sourced and cooked in accordance with Islamic ideas and mosques, is drawing more Muslim tourists to Japan (SG travellers, 2012). The availability of Halal food has become a more pressing issue due to the rise in Muslim tourists visiting Japan (Yusof & Shutto, 2014). In Japan, there are 55 halal food establishments and 61 mosques (Islamic Center Japan, 2012, reported in Yusof & Shutto, 2014). The top ten Halal-friendly vacation spots are Singapore (ranked #1), South Africa (ranked #2), Thailand (ranked #3), the United Kingdom (ranked #4), Bosnia & Herzegovina (ranked #5), India (ranked #6), Hong Kong (ranked #7), Germany (ranked #8), Australia (ranked #9), and Tanzania (ranked #10). These rankings are based on the quality of service and amenities that these destinations offer to Muslim travellers, as well as the marketing campaigns that target this market.

CHAPTER 3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Method

Data can be gathered through a variety of methods, including surveys, in-person meetings, and observation. It can also be examined using quantitative (statistical) or qualitative (non-statistical) methods, or a combination of both (Saunders et al., 2019; Sarantakos, 2013). Research methods can be broadly classified into two categories: qualitative and quantitative approaches. Three other approaches have been recognized by Jennings (2010): the mixed-method approach, indigenous methodologies, and cross-cultural methodologies. Most often, the term "quantitative" is used to refer to any method of gathering data (like a questionnaire) or method of analyzing data (like graphs or statistics) that produces or makes use of numerical data. Conversely, the term "qualitative" is mostly used to refer to any method of gathering data (like conducting an interview) or method of analyzing data (like classifying data) that produces or makes use of non-numerical data. As a result, data other than text, like images and videos, can be referred to as qualitative (Saunders et al., 2019). The quantitative approach to describing events involves gathering numerical data and utilizing mathematically based techniques, particularly statistics (Mujis, 2004, p. 1), for analysis. Multidisciplinary qualitative research employs a variety of methods to gather data, including structured and semi-structured interviews, participant and non-participant observation, document and material analysis, and verbal reporting of findings (Flick, 2014).

While it is easy to comprehend the distinctions between qualitative and quantitative research, it might be challenging to incorporate a certain methodology into a study. Numerous factors influence the research approach that is chosen for a project. Selecting and implementing the best research methodology is essential to addressing the research questions and achieving the study goal. There are arguments for and against qualitative research being better than quantitative research. Qualitative research can be particularly helpful in answering research questions in some disciplines of study, or vice versa. The researcher might select methods for data gathering and analysis after formulating the study question. According to Creswell and Creswell (2021), the goal of qualitative research is to identify recurring themes that emerge throughout the study process, while the goal of quantitative research is to generalize the findings to a larger study population.

Using references to Curran and Blackburn (2001), Saunders et al. (2019) assert that "many data collection techniques and analysis procedures can be used to answer research questions within business and management research." There isn't a single research strategy that is without flaws and restrictions. These affect the ability to provide accuracy, realism, and generalization. Accordingly, integrating quantitative and qualitative methodologies helps researchers avoid the drawbacks of relying just on one approach (Choi et al., 2020). According to Jennings (2001), when choosing a research methodology, it is important to take into account the study questions as well as constraints like time and resources. She added that the optimum approach for a study is to combine both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies in order to investigate the nature of the phenomenon and its extent, respectively.

In order to gather data and draw conclusions about the needs and travel habits of Muslim tourists, as well as the opportunities and difficulties presented by this niche market in Bangladesh's tourism industry, the researcher used both quantitative (statistical) and qualitative (non-statistical) techniques. This was done in addition to taking into account the findings of various research scholars and the research questions. When doing research, time and resources are also crucial components. Owing to time and financial limitations, the researcher only employed these two strategies in part.

The study employed a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to address research questions regarding the travel requirements and behaviors of Muslim tourists. Specifically, the quantitative method was used to determine the market potential of Muslim tourists, the difficulties in catering to this group, and destination recommendations for effectively serving this market segment.

Table 1 Research Objectives and Approaches

Objectives	Data source	Research Method	Data Collection Method
To understand the primary data behavior and travel requirements of Muslim visitors.	Primary data	Quantitative Approach	Questionnaire
To investigate how Islamic teaching affects Muslim travelers' needs and how it affects sociodemographic factors.	Primary data	Quantitative Approach	Questionnaire
To determine the alternatives that Muslim visitors to Bangladesh have for consuming halal goods and services.	Primary data	Quantitative Approach	Questionnaire
To investigate the possibilities of this market niche and the difficulties in offering services that are accommodating to Muslims seeking travel.	Primary data	Qualitative Approach	Interview
To make recommendations on how the tourism sector in Bangladesh may change to better serve Muslim visitors' requirements while respecting their religious convictions.	Primary data	Qualitative Approach	Interview

3.2 Respondents Collection and Time Frame

Only Muslim individuals, lodging facilities, dining establishments, and tour companies were contacted for this study. The individuals who traveled to Bangladesh between January 2021 and January 2022 filled out the questionnaire. Three categories were used to group the respondents: 1. Foreign Muslims 2. Bangladeshi restaurateurs, hoteliers, and tour guides the sites that were accessible for obtaining foreign Muslim respondents were universities, dorms, mosques, Muslim restaurants, and tourist destinations; the locations that were available for obtaining foreign respondents were student residences, Muslim restaurants, mosques, and virtual connections. Respondents were gathered for this purpose from Dinajpur, Rajshahi, Sylhet, Dhaka, and other convenient locations in Bangladesh. The necessary amount of data was gathered in around two months.

Table 2 Way of Questionnaire Respondent's Collection

Way of Collection	No. of Respondents
Personal visit	125
Internet (introducing this link through facebook, what'sapp and telephone)	85
E-mail	9

Initially, the researcher believed that interview subjects would be chosen from Dhaka and Sylhet; however, due to participant shortages and respondents' resistance, the researcher also made approaches in Rangpur, Dinajpur, and Mithapukur. In Bangladesh, these two cities are equally well-known for tourism. The goal of the study, the necessity to tape record the interview, and the confidentiality and anonymity of the information provided were all explained to the interviewees prior to the session. A few interview subjects refused to allow tape recording. In some instances, the respondents were given the interview questions to write their thoughts on, and the researcher just took notes. The duration of each interview was five to ten minutes. It would take longer to translate simultaneously, even though there weren't as many inquiries.

Table 3 Selection of Interviewees

Type of interviewee	Number	Method of Approaching	City in Bangladesh
Owners and workers of restaurants	7	Face to face interview	Dhaka, and Sylhet
Travel Agency Workers	7	Face to face as well as telephone conversation	Rangpur, Mithapukur, & Dinajpur
Hotel owners/ Employees	3	Face to face interview as well as telephone conversation	Rajshahi, and Bogra

CHAPTER 4 QUANTITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Demographic Analysis

The respondents' demographic profile is shown in Table 4. The target audience consisted of Muslim visitors visiting Bangladesh between January 2021 and January 2022 who were eighteen years of age or older. In all, 470 surveys were dispersed, with the goal of obtaining at least 300 valid responses. Only 219 of the 470 surveys that were distributed could be used for analysis, out of the 230 that were returned. These indicate a return rate of about 47%. Nine reusable questionnaires were obtained via email, eighty-five over the internet, and one hundred and five in person.

The majority of respondents, as indicated by Table 4, are in the 19–25-year-old (19–18) age range. They made up 45.2% of the sample ($n = 99$). Those over 25 (ages 26 to 35) came after this group. The individuals who participated in the above 35 years (36–45) and above 45 years (46–55) age categories comprised 11% ($n = 24$) and 5.5% ($n = 12$) of the sample, respectively, while this group accounted for 37.0% ($n = 81$) of the sample. Of all responders, 0.9% ($n = 2$) and 0.5% ($n = 1$) belonged to the age categories over 55 (56–65) and over 65 (66–above). The current results appear to be in line (with regard to the smallest group ground) with studies conducted by Zhang (2009) on tourists traveling from Bangladesh and Alsawafi (2013) on tourists traveling from Oman. Based on these investigations, it was found that the respondents who were over 65 made up the lowest group of respondents ($n = 2$), or 0.3% of all respondents. A study by Said et al. (2014) on evaluating consumers' understanding and religious belief in Malaysia's Halal cuisine and a study by Marzuki et al. (2014) on the assessment of managers demands toward Halal certification using factor analysis and clustering show that most respondents were in the age range of 20–30.

The majority of the sample respondents have bachelor's degrees in terms of education. Of all respondents, this education category comprised 39.7% ($n = 87$). The master education group, which accounted for 19.2% ($n = 42$) of all respondents, came next. The primary (or less) education group is the smallest representative education group (7.8%, $n = 17$), whereas the secondary and PhD or other degree groups made up 15.5% ($n = 34$) and 12.8% ($n = 28$) of the respondents, respectively. Thus, it can be concluded that the majority of respondents had a college degree, which is in line with Zhang's (2009), Alsawafi's (2013), and Said et al.'s (2014) findings.

As for occupation, Table 4 shows that 8.2%, 5.9%, 11.0%, 9.6%, 59.4%, and 5.9% of respondents were in the public sector, private sector, businessman, housewife, student, and other occupation groups, respectively. It was discovered that 130 respondents, or more, were students. Businessmen ($n = 24$) followed this group. Together, the private sector and other occupation categories had the lowest representation ($n = 13$ in each case).

It might be because, despite the fact that money is a factor for students, students in Bangladesh have more time during their semester break for travel than students in other groups. Regarding marital status, table 4 shows that 62.1% ($n = 136$) respondents were single, which represented the highest portion of total respondents. This is followed by the married respondent group, which included 79 respondents (36.1%). Widowed respondents represented the smallest portion of total respondents ($n = 4$, 1.8%).

Table 4, regarding religiousness and gender, also shows that 144 (65.8%) respondents were male and 75 (34.2%) were female. Religiousness variable data states that 46, 135, and 38 respondents thought themselves as mildly religious, religious, and very religious. Religious respondents represented the largest portion of the sample, which is 61.6%.

Table 4 states that a total of 23 countries accounted for 219 of the responses. Bangladesh accounted for the largest proportion of respondents, including over half of the sample (52.1%, $n = 115$). Pakistan, which accounted for 11.4% ($n = 25$) of all respondents, comes next. The proportion of respondents from Bangladesh and Indonesia was 10.5% ($n = 23$) and 9.1% (20), respectively. Nine (4.1%) of the respondents were Sudanese. Egypt, Palestine, India, Mauritania, Morocco, Yemen, Afghanistan, Algeria, Congo, Jordan, Kyrgyzstan, Niger,

Somalia, South Africa, Syria, Tajikistan, Tunisia, and Turkmenistan together represented 12.78% (n = 28) of the total respondents.

Table 4 Social and Demographic Details of the Participants

Category	Socio-demographic variables	Frequency	Percent
Age	Above 18 (19-25)	99	45.20%
	Above 25 (26-35)	81	37.00%
	Above 35 (36-45)	24	11.00%
	Above 45 (46-55)	12	5.50%
	Above 55 (56-65)	2	0.90%
	Above 65 (66-Above)	1	0.50%
	Total	219	100.00%
Level of Education	Primary (or less)	17	7.80%
	Secondary	34	15.50%
	Intermediate	11	5.00%
	Bachelor	87	39.70%
	Master	42	19.20%
	PhD or others	28	12.80%
	Total	219	100.00%
Occupation	Public servant	18	8.20%
	Private sector	13	5.90%
	Businessman	24	11.00%
	Housewife	21	9.60%
	Student	130	59.40%
	Other	13	5.90%
	Total	219	100.00%
Country	Bangladesh	23	10.50%

	China	114	52.10%
	Pakistan	25	11.40%
	Indonesia	20	9.10%
	Sudan	9	4.10%
	Egypt	4	1.80%
	Palestine	4	1.80%
	Mildly religious	46	21.00%
	Religious	135	61.60%
	Very religious	38	17.40%
	Total	219	100.00%
	Male	144	65.80%
Gender	Female	75	34.20%
	Total	219	100.00%

Factor-1: The first factor labeled "Halal food and respectful behavior" comprised eight items, which are shown in Food-related demands, are an important category of needs when traveling (Table 5). Numerous research investigations have found religious, cultural, social, psychological, and sensory acceptance variables that contribute to the complexity of food demand behavior. With an eigenvalue of 12.003, this factor in this study explained 38.72% of the total variance (Table 4). Table 5 shows that there was a substantial association between the eight items and the factor groupings they belong to, with each item having a factor loading of more than 0.515. It had a factor mean of 4.445 and a dependability Cronbach's alpha of 0.89. This component is consistent with the research conducted by Said et al. (2014), Alam & Sayuti (2011), Islam & Kärkkäinen (2013), Farahdel (2011), Alsawafi (2013), Tama & Voon (2014), and Rahman (2014), Mak et al. (2012); Rahman (2020); and Shakona (2015).

Table 5 Halal Food and Respectful Behavior

Items	Component 1
Shariah Law dictates that animals that are permitted shall be slaughtered.	.797
Islam forbids eating pig's flesh, carrion, or blood.	.785
I am unable to consume the flesh of dogs, lions, tigers, owls, eagles, and other carnivores.	.765
It is crucial to have halal signage on food packs and in restaurants and food outlets.	.707
When I travel, I have to have halal cuisine at the airport, hotels, and tourist attractions.	.705
I expect employees in hotels and restaurants to show respect for Islam.	.627

Food components, processing, and packaging really worry me.	.531
For me, the presence of halal cuisine at hotels and restaurants is crucial.	.518

Factor-2: The second factor, "Islamic hotel environment," had seven components. This component was able to capture 8.621% of the overall variance, with an eigenvalue of 2.673. This factor has a factor mean of 3.871 and a dependability Cronbach's alpha of 0.87. There is a high association between the items in Table 6's factor loading and the factor groupings to which they belong. For Muslim travelers, this is one of their basic demands, and they want the hotel atmosphere to fulfill their Islamic obligations. This dimension was also examined in the research conducted by Farahdel (2011), Alsawafi (2013), Samori & Sabtu (2014), Battour & Ismail (2014), Rahman (2014), and Shakona (2015).

Table 6 Halal Food and Respectful Behavior

Items	Component 2
Hotels with separate gyms and swimming pools for men and women.	.734
The hotel room must have a Qibla sticker or direction point towards Makkah city.	.731
I anticipate finding a Holy Qur'an copy in my hotel room.	.697
The authority forbade alcoholic beverages in the motel room.	.614
Hotels do not offer prostitute services.	.601
The hotel's Islamic dress code for its Muslim female employees	.549
An ablution facility is a necessary.	.517

Factor-3: Islamic morals constituted the third component and comprised four items. This factor had an eigenvalue of 1.584 and explained 5.108% of the variation in total. This factor's mean and reliability (Cronbach's alpha) are 3.97 and 0.71, respectively. Table 7 shows that all four items had factor loadings greater than 0.50, indicating a strong link between the items and the factor groupings they are a part of. The results of Alsawafi (2013), Battour & Ismail (2014), Shakona (2015), and Battour et al. (2013) also illustrated this factor.

Table 7 Islamic Morality

Items	Component 3
The destination government ought to permit Islamic clothing, such as the headscarf.	.682
I dislike clubs and discotheques that provide amusement at hotels.	.585
Women should have their own sections at beach destinations.	.558
Muslims worry about their safety, particularly when they go anywhere with a hijab-wearing lady.	.501

Factor-4: Three items are included in Table 8 under the category of amusement and worship, which is the fourth need component for Muslim travelers. This need component had an eigenvalue of 1.206 and explained 3.889% of the variation overall. Its dependable Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.73, with a factor mean of 3.71. A significant association between the items and the factor grouping they belong to is indicated by factor loadings above 0.590 in Table 8. In this regard, similar opinions were expressed by Farahdel (2011), Alsawafi (2013), Battour & Ismail (2014), Battour et al. (2013), Zamani-Farahani & Musa (2012), and Shakona (2015).

Table 8 Entertainment and Worship

Items	Component 4
For entertainment on a plane, at a hotel, etc., I want a TV channel.	.729
I need mosques to be accessible when visiting new places.	.606
For me, having a prayer room or amenities at tourist attractions, airports, retail centers, hotels, conference rooms, parks, etc. is crucial when traveling.	.594

Factor-5: Three items are grouped under the name Muslim Travel Need Factor, Washroom Facilities. "A good correlation was found between the items and the factor grouping to which they belong. The three items had a factor loading of over 0.520. Table 9 shows that this factor explained 3.767% of the total variance, with an eigenvalue of 1.168. The reliability of this factor was 0.76, with a factor mean of 17 The findings of Tai (2015) and Yusof & Muhammad (2013) supported this dimension.

Table 9 Wash Room Facilities

Items	Component 5
Water supply in toilets at tourism sites, airport, shopping mall, hotel, parks, etc. is very necessary for my destination selection.	.779
Cleaning vessel in the toilet is very necessary.	.759
Toilets positioned not to be face the direction of Mecca.	.522

Factor-6: The sixth factor was labelled destination choice. "It included only one item. This factor accounted for 3.312 of the total variance, with an eigenvalue of 1.027. The factor mean of this item is 2.50.

I utilized the sixth factor, which was labelled "destination choice" in the course of the given study to investigate its relevance as to the explanation of the consideration factors for travelers, as well as when selecting a vacation destination. It is vital to note that this factor, which also includes one item, sheds light on the associated implications and individuals' preferences to choose their place for a particular trip. It is also necessary to compose that other factors investigated in numerous studies with the consideration of groups, such as students, in determining their destination for visiting compete the sixth factor. However, the present course and Factor 6 provided an opportunity to explore the meaning of destination choice for Muslim behavior and the prospects of Halal tourism in Bangladesh in the sufficient details.

Items	6
I am not interested to visit non-Muslim country.	.800

4.1.1 Influence of Socio-demographic Variables

Islamic teachings influence the behavior of Muslim tourists, and the differences among different socio-demographic variables regarding Islamic teachings were assessed using descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, and an independent sample t-test. The role of sociodemographic variables (age, education level, occupation, marital status, religiousness, and gender) on the impact of Islamic teaching on Muslim tourists' travel behavior was examined using one-way ANOVA and an independent sample t-test.

4.1.1.1 The Influence of Age

Islamic teachings influence the behavior of Muslim tourists, and the differences among different socio-demographic variables regarding Islamic teachings were assessed using descriptive statistics, one-way ANOVA, and an independent sample t-test.

A one-way ANOVA was used to determine the differences in the impact of Islamic teaching on the travel behaviors of Muslim tourists across various age groups. The impact of Islamic education did not differ

significantly among age groups. The assumed significance level is 0.05, and every item has a significance level greater than 0.05 (table 10).

Table 10 Comparison of Influence of Islamic Teaching among Age Groups

Items	F	P
Islamic teachings affect my destination choice.	1.732	0.128
Islamic teachings affect my participation in some leisure activities.	.614	0.689
Islam encourages traveling to realize the greatness of God.	.424	0.832
The Shariah law forbids Muslims to visit places where one can be involved in Haram.	1.134	0.343
Traveling to Non-believers' country is dangerous to religious commitment and beliefs.	.957	0.348
Women cannot to travel without appropriate companion.	1.125	0.445

4.1.1.2 The Influence of Level of Education

Table 11 indicates that there was a statistically significant correlation found between the level of education and four travel behaviors. When compared to other education groups, the results showed that Islamic instruction had a significant influence on certain of the leisure activities of the intermediate education group ($F = 3.176$, $p < 0.01$). Higher-educated respondents may be better able to tie their understanding of Islam to their travel habits, while respondents with less education may not give a damn about how Islamic teachings affect their travel habits.

The outcome additionally demonstrated that 'realizing the greatness of God through traveling' has a significant impact on PhDs or other education groups ($F = 2.866$, $P < 0.05$). According to Table 11, the Shariah rule, which prohibits visiting locations where one can engage in Haram, has a significant impact on PhDs or other educated groups ($F = 2.636$, $P < 0.05$). Traveling to a place where there are non-believers had the greatest influence on the primary (or less) education group, according to the results ($F = 2.928$, $P < 0.05$). It makes sense to assume that this group misunderstands Islamic principles and lacks sufficient information about the country for non-believers.

Table 11 Comparison of Influence of Islamic Teaching among Education

Items	Mean						F	P
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Islamic teachings affect my some leisure activities.	2.82	2.82	4.00	3.40	3.64	3.50	3.161	0.009
Islam encourages traveling to realize the greatness of God.	3.65	3.53	4.00	4.00	3.98	4.50	2.866	0.016
The Shariah law forbids Muslims to visit places where one can be involved in Haram.	3.59	3.15	3.45	3.37	3.38	4.25	2.636	0.025
Traveling to Non-believers' country is dangerous to religious commitment & beliefs.	3.76	3.00	3.36	2.86	2.50	2.61	2.928	0.014

1. Primary (n-17)
2. Secondary (n-34)
3. Intermediate (11)
4. Bachelor (87)
5. Master (42)
6. PhD or others (28)

4.1.1.3 The Influence of Occupation

According to Table 12, there were two noteworthy variations in traveling behavior amongst various occupational categories. Table 12 displays only F-values that correspond to statistical values less than the 0.05

level. Housewives are more impacted by "realizing the greatness of God through traveling" ($F = 3.206$, $P < 0.01$) than are other occupational categories. Table 12 demonstrates how traveling to a nation of non-believers might have a detrimental impact on the housewife group's religious devotion and beliefs ($F = 2.667$, $P < 0.05$).

Table 12 Comparison of Influence of Islamic Teaching among Occupation

Items	Mean						F	P
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Islam encourages traveling to realize the greatness of God.	4.28	3.38	3.46	4.43	4.02	3.69	3.206	0.008
Traveling to Non-believers'	2.78	3.23	3.25	3.52	2.65	3.23	2.667	0.023

4.1.1.4 The Influence of Gender

Table 13 indicates that there was a solitary statistically significant variation between the sexes with respect to the impact of Islamic teachings on the travel habits of Muslim tourists. The findings showed that, in comparison to females, males are more influenced by the statement "women cannot travel without an appropriate companion" ($t = 3.707$, $P < 0.01$).

Table 13 Comparison of Influence of Islamic Teaching between genders

Items	Mean		T	P
	Male (n=144)	Female (n=75)		
Women cannot travel without appropriate companion.	3.81	3.15	3.707	0.000

CHAPTER 5 QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

5.1 Demographic Profile of the Interviewees

In order to gather information about the potential of the Muslim tourism market niche in Bangladesh, the difficulties in meeting the needs of Muslim tourists, and suggestions for meeting those needs, the researcher conducted 17 interviews.

In demographic table 14, it is seen that female participants (n = 9, 52.9%) were more than male participants (n = 8, 47.1%). It may be due to the fact that in service-oriented organizations, more female employees or workers work. In terms of age, the 31–40-year-old group was the largest participant group, followed by the 21–30-year-old (n = 3, 17.6%) and 41–50-year-old (n = 3, 17.6%) groups, respectively. There were 10 interviewees in the 31–40 age groups, which represented 58.8% of the participants. The smallest age group (51 and older) had only one participant. Regarding the type of organization, Muslim restaurants and Muslim service-providing travel agencies were 7 (41.2%) and 7 (41.2%), respectively. Three interviews were conducted in Muslim hotels, which represented 17.6% of the total participants.

Table 14 also shows that the majority of the participants were managers of the organizations, which represented 82.4% (14) of the total participants. 2 participants were owners of the organization, which indicated 11.8% of the total interviewees, and 1 participant was a waitress in a Muslim restaurant.

Table 14 Demographic Profile of the Participants

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	9	52.9%
Male	8	47.1%
Total	17	100.0%
Age		
(21-30) Age	3	17.6%
(31-40) Age	10	58.8%
(41-50) Age	3	17.6%
(51-Above) Age	1	5.9%
Total	17	100.0%
Type of the organization		
Muslim hotel and Muslim restaurant	3	17.6%
Muslim service providing travel Agencies	7	41.2%
Total	7	41.2%
Total	17	100.0%
Position		
Manager	14	82.4%
Owner	2	11.8%
Waitress	1	5.9%
Total	17	100.0%

5.2 Challenges for Catering Muslim Tourism Market

Travel agents and destination marketers cannot ignore the Muslim tourism sector, as it is one of the fastest-growing market categories. Many non-Muslim travel destinations are currently vying for the attention of this sizable market niche. Various locations have various obstacles to meeting the needs of Muslim tourists. Here, the researcher spoke with Muslim operators of travel agencies, hotels, and restaurants to learn about the

difficulties they encounter in providing services to both domestic and foreign Muslim travellers. The researcher determined eight problems after examining every interview. These are listed below:

1. Lack of enough facilities:

By providing the same amenities, Islamic tourism has drawn travellers from all over the world, including non-Muslims. However, in order to draw Muslim visitors, non-Muslim places must make certain accommodations specifically tailored to their needs. Muslim travellers are not like other travellers. They want prayer rooms, Muslim restaurants, and Halal cuisine. These are essential requirements for Muslim travellers. When it comes to halal food, they have zero tolerance. However, Bangladesh is a Muslim country where these amenities are sufficient.

2. Limited Suppliers:

Maintaining partnerships with relevant service providers is imperative in order to enable Muslim tourists to access services that comply with Halal standards. Restaurants serving Muslims must purchase meat and other halal ingredients in order to produce halal dishes. They can purchase beef, mutton, and poultry from Muslim vendors who perform animal sacrifices in accordance with Shariah laws. There are a lot of them in Bangladesh.

3. Lack of knowledgeable staff:

In addition to being able to anticipate and read the demands of customers, service staff members must often engage with people from a variety of racial and religious backgrounds. Staff members must get familiar with the subtleties of serving Muslim tourists in order to better meet their specific demands. They must be aware of the location of the closest mosque, Makkah's direction, the times of the daily prayers, the location of the Muslim eatery, etc.

4. High Cost:

The concentration of halal goods and raw materials is low in Bangladesh. Bangladesh offers inexpensive halal materials. They must purchase raw materials or halal goods from some Muslim stores, where the supply of halal goods is extremely limited but the cost is exorbitant. Because it wouldn't significantly raise the price of halal products or cause them to become unavailable in some countries or regions, suppliers to the Muslim world, such as Bangladesh, don't have to maintain a designated storage zone or racks for halal raw materials or products. Instead, they have dedicated infrastructure for halal goods.

5. Lack of Muslim chef:

In restaurants, the chef is crucial to the preparation of Halal food. The chef ought to be well-versed in halal ingredients, halal meat, and halal raw materials. Islam makes no mention of the need to be a Muslim in order to offer Halal food or meat. Every chef in the area is familiar with Muslim cuisine. In Bangladesh, finding a Muslim cook is simple.

6. Dealing with non-Muslim customers:

Since the majority of visitors to Bangladesh are Muslims, halal eateries have an easy time surviving as a Muslim-majority nation. In Bangladesh's major cities, such as Dhaka, Rangpur, and Rajshahi, it is quite rare to find wine served at Halal restaurants. Only five-star hotels and restaurants are served by it. Alcohol and wine are absolutely forbidden in Bangladesh.

7. Achieving trust:

Muslim travellers have extremely high standards for goods and services. Travellers who practice Islam can visit Bangladesh. For Bangladesh, Muslim tourists do not represent a totally new market niche. Bangladesh lacks a well-known standards system or strong brand to attest to the Halal friendliness of hotels, resorts, cruise ships, restaurants, airports, and parks. Non-Muslim travel countries such as Singapore, Thailand, New Zealand, France, the USA, and Australia have already established a positive reputation and standardized Halal food, which helps build Muslim traveller's confidence that they can easily get Halal facilities there.

8. Language barrier:

While speaking with Muslim travellers is not particularly difficult, nearly every interviewee mentioned having a language barrier. There are linguistic barriers to accommodating different types of foreign visitors who speak different languages.

CHAPTER 6 CONCLUSION

6.1 Research Conclusion

The goal of the study was to improve knowledge and comprehension of Muslim tourists' traveling needs and behaviors by learning more about Muslim travellers' needs, the impact of Islamic teachings on Muslim travel behavior and how it relates to socio-demographic factors, alternative options for consuming Halal goods and services, the potential of this market, the difficulties in serving this market, and suggestions for the Bangladeshi tourism sector to meet this market.

The research's quantitative component found that when Muslim tourists travel to Muslim countries like Bangladesh, they must have access to halal cuisine, courteous behavior, an Islamic hotel atmosphere, Islamic morality, entertainment and places of worship, clean restroom facilities, and a variety of destinations. It also showed that certain travel behaviors such as appreciating the magnificence of God, women's travel, and visiting locations where one can engage in Haram are strongly influenced by Islamic teachings, while other travel behaviors such as engaging in leisure activities, selecting a destination, and visiting nations where there are no Muslims are less influenced.

Additionally, it was demonstrated from a socio-demographic perspective that the education group is impacted by engaging in certain leisure activities, realizing the magnificence of God, going to locations where one can engage in Haram, and traveling to countries where believers reside; the occupation group housewives are the most affected group is impacted by realizing the magnificence of God and traveling to countries where believers reside; the religious group the most affected group is impacted by realizing the magnificence of God and women's travels without suitable companionship; and men are more influenced by the Islamic precept that women cannot go alone. Age and marital status, the other two socio-demographic factors, did not significantly differ in their representation of Islamic beliefs.

This quantitative portion also revealed that Muslims visiting other countries have the option to substitute eating marine food vegetables, fish, and fruits for Halal goods and services. The qualitative portion of the study produced results that showed the Muslim tourist sector has sizable potential and a youthful demographic.

The respondents perceive Muslim tourism as a relatively intriguing phenomenon and a recent development in the travel industry. It has the potential to grow Bangladeshi tourism-related industries, including those that provide tour services, Halal restaurants, and Halal cuisine. In addition, eight obstacles related to catering to Muslim visitors were highlighted in this part. These challenges included inadequate facilities, a shortage of Halal material suppliers, a shortage of qualified staff, high costs, and the absence of a Muslim chef, interacting with non-Muslim clients, building trust, and language barriers. It also made nine recommendations for the government and tourism sector in Bangladesh to meet the demands of Muslim travellers and get past obstacles. The recommendations include making sure that Halal food is available, building hotels that are welcoming to Muslims, creating a separate tourism department within the government for Muslim visitors, drafting agreements related to tourism, offering training programs for tourism personnel, advertising, empowering the role of Muslim leaders in the tourism industry, opening souvenir shops for Muslim visitors, and developing smart phone applications in Arabic, English, and other languages.

Ultimately, it can be said that the study was successful in identifying the requirements and travel habits of Muslim visitors and in offering the Bangladeshi tourism and hospitality sector important knowledge and expertise.

6.2 Implications for Practice

The study's conclusions provide some useful recommendations for non-Muslim travel destinations, with Bangladesh's tourism and hospitality sectors in particular being attractive to and able to satisfy a sizable Muslim market niche. The research's overall conclusions highlighted some particular travel requirements that

Bangladesh should prioritize as a Muslim destination if it hopes to lead the global tourism industry in the future. The following are some further particular recommendations that should be put into practice:

1. For Muslim travellers, halal food is an absolute necessity. Muslim travellers are unable to give up on this requirement. Thus, it is recommended that the Bangladesh tourism sector make sure that Halal cuisine is available close to the tourist attractions. There should be more establishments of halal eateries. There should be more establishments of halal eateries. Both Muslim and non-Muslim travellers' dietary preferences can be simultaneously satisfied by this eatery.

2. It is also advised that the government of Bangladesh progressively concentrate on other particular requirements of Muslim travellers, such as hotels that are friendly to Islam, making sure that there are facilities for prayer, and installing water-efficient toilets.

3. To position Bangladesh as a hassle-free travel destination for Muslim travellers, tour operators operating in Bangladesh must have distinctive branding or taglines aimed at this demographic. In this regard, a marketing and promotion effort is advised.

4. It is strongly advised that Bangladeshi academics conduct more research on this topic and that government officials conduct real-world studies regarding this business possibility.

5. At the moment, Bangladeshi is the language used in location identification apps. These applications ought to be available in English since they highlight travel. Muslim travellers will find it easier to locate Halal eateries, Muslim-only lodgings, mosques, etc. with the use of these apps.

6. There are a lot of Islamic heritage sites, cuisines, and civilizations in Bangladesh. These are crucial at first to draw in Muslim travellers. It is advised that those revered locations and legacies be developed.

7. It's also critical to provide competent tour guides and operators with the necessary training regarding the needs and wants of Muslim tourists. It is advised that Islamic organizations and Muslim leaders in Bangladesh be included in this training initiative.

8. Bangladesh currently enjoys cordial ties with all of the Arabian nations as well as Muslim nations, including Sudan, Malaysia, Indonesia, Pakistan, and Turkey.

Thus, it is advised to establish travel and tourism agreements with the governments and tour operators of those nations. Ultimately, based on the results of prior studies and interviews, it can be concluded that Bangladesh has been far behind in meeting the needs of the Muslim market segment. Even though its neighbors, Singapore, Japan, Korea, and Thailand, are working hard to get a commercial advantage from this market, Bangladesh has not yet made the necessary moves to take control of it. Finally, but just as importantly, Bangladesh should look into the Muslim tourism market and take action to attract and serve this sizable market niche if it wants to be a competitive global leader in the tourism industry.

6.3 Limitations

This study has limitations that need to be noted, just like any other thesis study. These are

1. To begin with, the study's convenience sample size and snowball sampling for the quantitative portion are its main limitations. Convenience sampling was used because of the small sample size and limitations in terms of time, money, and resources. These had an impact on how broadly the research's conclusions might be applied.

2. The nature of religiosity is intimate and delicate. Bangladesh is a Muslim nation. The study's subject is extremely delicate for Bangladeshi Muslims who participated in it. Some interviewees were found to be unwilling to provide ideas to the government regarding the promotion of Muslim tourism. This somewhat constrained the research findings.

3. One major barrier to conducting research in Bangladesh is language. It was discovered that respondents occasionally expressed fear towards English-speaking researchers and foreigners. They answered the interview questions in a very restrained and cautious manner. It had an impact on the interview procedure.

4. Previous research on Muslim visitors to Bangladesh was lacking. As a result, many of the research's conclusions could not be compared to or supported by those of other studies.

6.4 Future Direction

The direction of future research that comes from the current investigation is crucial to improving the findings of the current study. To guarantee greater generalizability of the findings, a comprehensive mixed-methods research approach with a sizable sample size can be used in subsequent studies. Future research can employ interview participants from other Bangladeshi cities and towns, while the interviews for this study were limited to five cities. Furthermore, more research is necessary to provide more in-depth insights into the demands and behavior of Muslim tourists, as this study only represents a first attempt to explore this topic. Additionally, while this study only included Sunni Muslims, Shiite Muslims may potentially be included in representative samples in future research.

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